

The study on Marketing Strategies of Social E-commerce Platforms by AISAS Theory - Taking Kuaishou as an Example

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Abstract: Against the backdrop of rapid updates and iterations of the Internet, the rise of short videos has made Social E-Commerce a new business model. Using the Kuaishou platform as a case study, this paper aims to explore marketing strategies for Social Networking Site from the perspective of AISAS theory. Through literature review, case analysis, in-depth interviews, and content analysis, it reveals Kuaishou's current practices in attracting users' attention, stimulating interest, promoting searches, driving actions, and encouraging sharing, as well as identifying major issues faced by the platform, including content quality, user experience, brand image, pricing and promotions, and technical functions. The paper provides optimization strategies for Kuaishou, primarily focusing on improving content quality, enhancing user experience, reshaping brand image, optimizing pricing strategy, and increasing investment in technological innovation, in order to enhance marketing effectiveness and competitiveness, and achieve sustainable development. This study not only enriches the application of AISAS theory in the Social E-Commerce environment, but also offers directions for optimizing marketing strategies for Social E-Commerce platforms.

Keywords: AISAS Theory, Social E-commerce Platform, Marketing Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of the Internet, society, the economy, and lifestyles have undergone tremendous changes, making life more convenient and efficient. Technological advances have fueled the growth of e-commerce, and along with the rise of short videos, Social E-Commerce has become a new business model. The widespread adoption of mobile internet has enabled Social Networking Site to rise swiftly and become a part of people's daily lives. As of December 2024, the number of online shopping users in China had reached 974 million, accounting for 87.9% of all internet users ^[1]. Online shopping is faster and more convenient, and consumers tend to prefer it. Moreover, when consumers have positive experiences with products or services, they are more inclined to share them with others via social platforms. While the development and marketing of Social Networking Site have achieved notable success, they also face numerous challenges, such as inconsistent product quality. This issue not only affects user experience but also limits the platform's growth, requiring further research and solutions.

Many scholars have studied Social E-Commerce in terms of its current development status, influencing factors, and consumer willingness. Although there is considerable research on marketing strategies, studies from the perspective of the AISAS theory are insufficient. This paper takes Kuaishou as the research subject, applying the AISAS theory to the marketing strategy analysis of Social Networking Site, and explores the applicability of this theory in the Social E-Commerce environment. This enriches both AISAS theory and marketing strategy theory, while identifying problems and optimization measures in individual case marketing strategies to enhance competitiveness and ultimately achieve sustainable corporate development.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. AISAS Theory

In 2005, Japan's Dentsu Inc., in response to changes in consumer behavior, proposed the AISAS model based on the traditional AIMDA model. The AISAS theory is better suited to the marketing environment of the digital era. The AISAS model consists of five components: Attention, Interest, Search, Action, and Share. Attention refers to consumers noticing a product through various channels. Interest arises when consumers, having noticed the product, develop curiosity and actively seek to learn more about it. Search involves satisfying their needs by researching the product in greater depth and making comparisons. Action refers to the consumer deciding to make a purchase and completing the buying process. Share occurs when, after purchasing a product, consumers post reviews and feedback through social media and other platforms, achieving a form of sharing. This creates valuable content and information, enabling continuous traffic growth and attracting more new users [2].

The AISAS theory is applied in areas such as consumer behavior, social media marketing, and digital marketing. Authors Mingjie, Luo Gan, and others (2022) combined the AISAS model to replan sports brands to attract tourists, stimulate their interest, and enhance consumers' purchase intention, providing solutions for the development of the sports tourism industry [3]. Shi Yanchun (2020) found through the AISAS model that self-media platforms serve as a bridge between enterprises and users, can facilitate consumer actions, and help improve user loyalty [4]. Sun Yufei (2021), based on the AISAS model, studied the short-video marketing model of beauty internet celebrities, proposing high-quality content marketing to precisely meet consumer needs and build trust with consumers [5].

In this study, the AISAS theory is used as the theoretical framework for analyzing Social Networking Site's marketing strategy, with a particular focus on how Social Networking Site's marketing strategy attracts consumer attention, arouses interest, encourages information search, drives purchasing behavior, and promotes sharing and dissemination.

B. Social Networking Site

In recent years, Social E-Commerce has developed rapidly, conducting e-commerce transactions through social relationships and channels such as social media software. Chinese scholars mainly divide Social E-Commerce into the following three models: first, 'E-commerce + Social' such as Pinduoduo; second, 'Social + E-commerce' such as Kuaishou; third, 'Virtual Community + E-commerce' such as Xiaohongshu. Abudureheman Abuduaine (2020) proposed that Social E-Commerce mainly has three models: social sharing e-commerce model, social content e-commerce model, and social retail e-commerce model, with representative platforms being Pinduoduo, Xiaohongshu, and Yunji Weidian [6].

Social Networking Site integrates social and e-commerce functions. The research on Social E-Commerce mainly explores aspects such as user behavior studies, business model analysis, and technology acceptance. Wang Yuehui, Liu Shuang, and others (2021) believe that B2C Social Networking Site can enhance user experience by creating social value, time value, and economic value [7]. Huang Sihao, Xiao Jincen, et al. (2020) indicate that the interactive atmosphere and supportive environment of Social Networking Site have a significant positive impact on consumers' continuous purchase intentions [8]. Dai Yuting (2024) proposes that in Xiaohongshu's B2K2C (Business to KOC/KOL to Consumer) business model, KOCs have a significant correlation with user cognition, enhancing users' perception of the platform and improving their experience [9]. Yan Linfei (2020) found that network effects positively influence perceived ease of use and are closely related to continuous user intention [10]. Li (2024) proposed four key factors influencing Social Networking Site's attractiveness: access, conversion, loyalty, and sharing [11].

In this study, Kuaishou was chosen as an e-commerce platform primarily focused on short videos and live streaming, while also implementing the Social E-Commerce function through formats such as small shops. This paper mainly analyzes how Kuaishou's marketing strategies attract consumers' attention, stimulate interest, encourage information search, drive purchasing behavior, and promote sharing and dissemination.

C. Marketing Strategy

Marketing strategy refers to a series of plans and actions taken by a company, based on its internal and external competitive conditions, with customer needs as the starting point, to achieve marketing objectives. Yuan (2020) applied the 4P theory to analyze TikTok and concluded that clearly defining the target user group and product positioning is key, while strengthening product development and actively responding to localization strategies are important factors for success [12]. Hu (2023), based on the 4P and 4C theories and integrated marketing communications, proposed a consumer-centered approach that fosters emotional identification between the brand and consumers to maintain long-term customer value [13].

With the development of the times, companies adopt multi-channel marketing strategies to ensure a consistent service experience across different customer touchpoints, such as content marketing, social media marketing, mobile marketing, and data-driven marketing. Sohaib (2022) indicated that Social E-Commerce marketing has become a key driving force for growth in the field of e-commerce ^[14]. Huang (2022) analyzed the behavioral interactions among opinion leaders, product recommendations, and consumer purchasing decisions, and found that the larger or smaller the transaction proportion, the lower the recommendation cost, and the greater the psychological impact on consumers ^[15]. Yang Zhengzheng (2022) pointed out that in Social E-Commerce marketing there are problems such as limited sales channels, imperfect regulatory mechanisms, and insufficient customer service ^[16]. In this study, Social Networking Site's marketing activities leverage the characteristics of social networks, designed to promote the dissemination and sales of products on the platform through user-generated content and deep social interaction.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Case Introduction

Kuaishou, founded in 2011, is one of China's most popular short video platforms and also known as Social Networking Site. In addition to short video sharing and livestream shopping, it features local social networking and mini-theatre functions, enabling users to record and share bits of their daily life and interact with other users in real time. Users can also explore local content to discover nearby people and events, as well as create and watch short plays to enrich their entertainment experience. In 2020, Kuaishou allowed users to purchase JD.com products directly from the platform. Kuaishou has cultivated many popular livestream hosts, and users with shopping needs can search for product information from their favorite hosts.

Most of Kuaishou's users are located in third-tier cities and below, with a large proportion in fourth-tier cities and below. The majority of Kuaishou's users are under the age of 35. It helps promote the sales of agricultural products and cultural dissemination, effectively enhancing the platform's influence. Younger groups are more receptive to the internet, more willing to record and share their lives, interact with other users, have personalized needs, and show significant purchasing intent. In 2021, Kuaishou was successfully listed on the Main Board of the Hong Kong Stock Exchange, which not only brought more financial support to the company but also boosted its reputation and influence.

B. Current Marketing Situation under the AISAS Model

Analyze Kuaishou's current marketing strategy using the AISAS theory, as shown in TABLE 1.

C. Interview Analysis

In order to gain a deeper understanding of consumers' views on Kuaishou platform marketing strategies, Dworkin (2012) suggested that the appropriate sample size for in-depth interviews in qualitative research ranges from 5 to 50 interviewees ^[17]. Fourteen interviewees were invited, aged between 18 and 35, including 8 females and 6 males, to participate in semi-open in-depth interviews. The interview data were further organized and systematically summarized

TABLE 1: KUAISHOU'S MARKETING STRATEGIES UNDER AISAS THEORY

	Product	Price	Place	Promotion
Attention	1. Provide diversified content such as videos, live streams, and products. 2. Give priority to recommending positive content.	1. The price is positioned at a mid-range level, offering high cost performance. 2. Allow users to register and use for free, with a relatively low threshold.	1. Channels that draw users' attention through livestreams and advertisements. 2. In addition to collaborating with third-party platforms, it also has its own platforms, such as 'Kuaishou Shop'.	1. Promotion through advertising 2. Combine user characteristics to deliver targeted advertisements and attract attention.
Interest	Recommend content that the user may be interested in based on their personal needs and preferences Interesting content.	The platform distributes discounts and benefits through holiday marketing or its own promotional activities.	Increase topic exposure and discussion through live streaming and advertising.	Collaborate with brands for joint marketing campaigns, organize promotional activities, and enhance user engagement and participation.

Search	1. The user searches for products based on personal needs or preferences. 2. The platform provides specific search windows,	Push promotions and advertisements based on the user's search content.	Cooperate with other platforms, such as recommendation and review features on rednote.	The platform increases the frequency of search content appearances through algorithmic recommendations and push mechanisms.
Action	The platform presents product information combined with video explanations to stimulate the desire to purchase.	1. Simplify the purchasing process 2. Provide multiple payment methods.	Video links and live streaming rooms are the main purchasing channels, with convenient and quick access.	During the live broadcast, the host's recommendations and the discounts in the live room are substantial, with many
Share	Encourage users to share their shopping experiences with products or content they are satisfied with.	Promote sales conversion by sharing this action.	Collaborate with other social media platforms to make it easier and faster for users to share content from Kuaishou.	Build a community with a positive atmosphere, leveraging the community effect to encourage users to share and communicate.

and analyzed using content analysis to identify the characteristics of the interview content, extract valid information, and provide in-depth and practical recommendations.

TABLE 2(a)(b) mainly summarizes the marketing opinions of 14 interviewees on the Kuaishou platform in five dimensions: attention, interest, search, action, and sharing, providing insights into consumers' overall evaluation and preferences for the Kuaishou.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Existing problems

Based on a comprehensive literature review, case analysis, and interview results, the main issues in Kuaishou platform's marketing strategies are identified as follows:

1. Content Quality Issues

Kuaishou is both a short video platform and an e-commerce platform. Watching videos on the platform is a commonly used feature, but 57.14% of interviewees are still dissatisfied with the current innovation and quality of video content. "The material creation is not rich enough" (Interviewee A, interview date: November 29, 2024) indicates that users expect to see more diverse and innovative content. "The content is somewhat vulgar and outdated" (Interviewee M, interview date: December 2, 2024) reflects that users have higher expectations regarding the content.

2. User Experience Issues

User experience can affect user retention. 50% of interviewees felt that the overall user experience was acceptable but had shortcomings. "The delivery speed is fine, but sometimes the goods don't match the description" (Interviewee E, interview date: November 30, 2024). "The customer service entry is hard to find and laggy" (Interviewee K, interview date: December 2, 2024), which has already directly affected the user experience. It has also impacted the social interaction experience and the supportive environment.

3. Brand Image Issues

Kuaishou's brand image is not very clear. Only 35.71% of interviewees are interested in live streaming on the platform, while 64.29% are more interested in videos. They hold negative opinions about live streaming content and the Kuaishou platform, describing it as 'a bit tacky' (Interviewee J, interview date: December 2, 2024) and 'strongly regional' (Interviewee A, interview date: November 29, 2024), which affects users' overall evaluation of the platform. 'Few big-name streamers, high user attrition rate' (Interviewee H, interview date: December 1, 2024). A lack of influential streamers may weaken the platform's appeal.

4. Price Promotion Issues

Price is an important factor influencing purchasing behavior, with 53.85% of respondents being relatively sensitive to promotional activities. "The price advantage is not significant" (Interviewee I, interview date: December 1, 2024), "The discount is not large enough" (Interviewee J, interview date: December 2, 2024). This reflects users' dissatisfaction with pricing strategies, believing that the price advantage is not obvious.

TABLE 2(a) INTERVIEW CONTENT ANALYSIS-ATTENTION NAD INTEREST

AISAS	Topic	Item	Answer	Count	Percentage(%)	
Attention	Function or Service	Function	Video	11	27.50	
			Live broadcast	11	27.50	
			Shopping	11	27.50	
			Social Interaction	5	12.50	
			Game	2	5.00	
			Service	Same city	4	57.14
				Check in	2	28.57
	Information of Attention	Content	Life	1	14.29	
			Video	9	60.00	
			Live broadcast	6	40.00	
			Product-related	Price	8	66.67
				The product itself	4	33.33
			Promotional Event	Promotion	5	100.00
			Social Activity	Hot Topic	1	100.00
Channel		Recommendation	11	50.00		
		Social Sharing	6	27.27		
		Search	5	22.73		
		Information that sparks interest	Content	Video	9	64.29
Live broadcast	5			35.71		
Product-related	Price			4	57.14	
	The product itself			3	42.86	
Promotional Event	Promotion			3	100.00	
Interest	Channel			Search	6	31.58
				User Reviews	4	21.05
		Other platforms	4	21.05		
		Live streaming room	3	15.79		
		Product Introduction	2	10.53		

TABLE 2(b) INTERVIEW CONTENT ANALYSIS —SEARCH, ACTION AND SHARE

AISAS	Topic	Item	Answer	Count	Percentage(%)	
Search	Active Search Factor	Economy	Promotional Event	7	53.85	
			Price	6	46.15	
			Content	Personal interest	2	66.67
				Video	1	33.33
			Demand	Product	3	75.00
	Living needs	1		25.00		
	The most influential promotional information		User Reviews	10	71.43	
			Platform Recommendation	3	21.43	
			Spokesperson and livestream	1	7.14	
	Action	Purchase Action Factor	Content	Video	3	60.00
Live streaming				2	40.00	
Price				Discount	5	50.00
		Discounted price	5	50.00		
Promotional Activity			Live-streaming sales	9	75.00	
			Recommended by the Host	3	25.00	
Purchase Channel			Live streaming room	11	50.00	

AISAS	Topic	Item	Answer	Count	Percentage(%)		
Share			Platform Store	9	40.91		
			Video link	2	9.09		
	Sharing status	Yes		Good product quality	6	46.15	
				Affordable price	4	30.77	
				Personal feelings, interesting	3	23.08	
				No	4	80.00	
				Unless compensated	1	20.00	
	Share Kuaishou Information	Goods and Services		Product	5	83.33	
				Service	1	16.67	
		Offers and Discounts		Promotional Offers	5	83.33	
				Discounts	1	16.67	
		Rewards and Activities		Reward	6	60.00	
				Invite Friends Event	4	40.00	
		Channel	Kuaishou Platform		Direct forward	2	50.00
					Private message	2	50.00
			Other Platforms		WeChat	13	48.15
					QQ	4	14.81
	rednote				2	7.41	
	TikTok				2	7.41	
	Weibo				2	7.41	
Zhihu	2				7.41		
Tieba	2	7.41					

5. Technical Function Issues

33.33% of respondents believe that the platform has unique technological innovation features, but 66.67% of respondents expect more innovative functions or services. "Expanded authority for AI customer service" (Interviewee E, interview date: November 30, 2024), "Integrated and convenient" (Interviewee M, interview date: December 2, 2024).

B. Optimization Strategies

In response to the existing problems mentioned above, the following marketing strategy optimization measures are proposed:

1. Improve content quality

Establish a stricter content review mechanism, leveraging new technologies such as artificial intelligence to identify and filter out low-quality and vulgar content, and strengthen supervision. Formulate incentive policies to encourage high-quality creation and positive content. Cooperate with other brands to introduce more materials and special effects, enriching creative resources. Additionally, launch creative activities with diverse video formats and themes to attract more user participation.

2. Improve User Experience

Optimize the user interface and establish an efficient customer service system—introduce AI customer service, official Q&A, and community self-service, reducing user wait time and responding quickly to user needs. Maintain platform stability and smooth performance. Expand sales channels and offer a more diversified range of products and services to meet user demands.

3. Reshape Brand Image

Collaborate with well-known brands and celebrities to hold joint events, brand promotions, and advertising campaigns to enhance brand image, support diverse content creation, attract user groups with different interests and backgrounds, and reduce the influence of regional labels. In addition, participate more in public welfare activities to positively promote brand values and change users' negative perceptions of Kuaishou as "tacky" or "vulgar."

4. Optimize pricing strategy

Monitor competitors' price changes in real time, and adjust your own prices flexibly based on consumer purchasing behavior data. Regularly launch promotional activities such as 'limited-time discounts' and 'spend-and-save offers.' Combine with holiday marketing to offer attractive prices and entice users to buy. The platform can also occasionally push questionnaires to survey users' purchase intentions and experiences, to promptly understand user feedback.

5. Increase technological innovation

Increase investment in the research and development of artificial intelligence technologies, enhance content algorithms, and develop new features such as AI customer service, intelligent search, and virtual reality (VR). This will help strengthen user engagement through interaction and content creation, thereby improving service quality and user satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

Taking Kuaishou as a case study and applying literature research, in-depth interviews, and case study methods, this paper explores the platform's marketing strategies using the AISAS theory. The study finds that Kuaishou has unique characteristics and achievements compared to other platforms, but still faces issues in content quality, user experience, brand image, price competitiveness, and technical functions. The proposed optimization measures include enhancing content quality, improving user experience, reshaping brand image, optimizing pricing strategies, and increasing investment in technological innovation. By implementing these measures, Kuaishou can better meet user needs, improve user satisfaction, strengthen brand competitiveness, and maintain a leading position in the fierce market competition.

In summary, as a Social Networking Site, Kuaishou's marketing strategy needs to be continuously adjusted and optimized according to market changes and user needs. By thoroughly understanding and applying the AISAS theory, Kuaishou can more effectively attract and retain users, promote purchasing behavior, encourage user sharing, enhance the platform's competitiveness, and thereby achieve sustainable long-term development.

REFERENCES

- [1] The 55th "Statistical Report on the Development of the Internet in China" Released. (2025). *Media Forum*, 9(02):121.
- [2] Ji, H.H., Liu, J. (2021). Comparative Study on Group Purchase Guidance Strategies of Community Group-Buying E-commerce Based on the AISAS Consumer Behavior Model. *National Circulation Economy*, (20): 22-24.
- [3] Ming, J., Luo, G., Ran, M.G.. (2022). Research on the Consumption Behavior Path of Sports Tourism in Guizhou Province under the AISAS Model. *Bulletin of Sports Science and Technology Literature*, 30(03): 185-188.
- [4] Shi, Y.C.. (2020). Analysis of Self-Media Marketing Strategies Based on the AISAS Model—Taking 'Li Ziqi' as an Example. *China Industrial Economy*, (20):55-56.
- [5] Sun, Y.F. (2021). Dual case study on short video marketing of beauty products based on the AISAS model. *Jiangsu Business Review*, (01):37-40+45.
- [6] Abdurrahman,·Abduaini & Xie, Ying. (2020). Research on Social E-Commerce Business Model Innovation Based on Multiple Case Comparisons. *Economic Forum*, (10): 123-132.
- [7] Wang, Y.H., Liu, Shuang, Tang, S.N., et al. (2021). Measurement and Empirical Study on the Quality of Online Shopping Experience for B2CSocial Networking Site Customers. *Journal of Beijing Institute of Technology (Social Sciences Edition)*, 23(03):71-85.
- [8] Huang, S.H., Xiao, J.C., Jin, Y.N.. (2020). A Study on the Factors Influencing Consumers' Continuous Purchase Intention of Social Networking Site Based on the S-O-R Theory. *Soft Science*, 34(06):115-121.
- [9] Dai, Y.T. (2024). Research on the B2K2C Business Model of Social Networking Site Xiaohongshu. *Modern Business*, (05):3-6.
- [10] Yan, L.F. (2020). Research on Social Networking Site Users' Continuous Usage Intention Based on the Technology Acceptance Model. *Modern Business Trade Industry*, 41(18): 40-41.

- [11] Jing L., Ruiqi Y., Wei L., et al. (2024). Study on the attractiveness of social e-commerce platforms from the consumers' perspective based on the AISAS model. *Journal of Computational Methods in Sciences and Engineering*, 24(4-5): 2517-2547.
- [12] Weilin, Y., Yue, M., Qi, S. (2020). Research on the International Marketing Strategy of TikTok -- Based on the Analysis of 4P Theory. *Frontiers in Educational Research*, 3(14): 138-150.
- [13] Hu, Z., Wang, C., Xu, Z. (2023). Integrated marketing communication and new media strategy for the domestic industry based on 4P and 4C theory. *The Frontiers of Society, Science and Technology*, 5(5):113-117.
- [14] Muhammad, S., Ali, A. S., Abdul, M.. (2022). Role of social media marketing activities in China's e-commerce industry: A stimulus-organism-response theory context. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13: 941058.
- [15] Huang, X., Huo, Y. (2021). Research on Decision-Making Behavior of Social E-Commerce Marketing Subjects. *Francis Academic Press*, 3(15):152-158.
- [16] Yang, Z.Z., An, Q. (2022). Marketing Strategies and Countermeasure Suggestions for Social E-Commerce—A Case Study of Yunji Micro Store. *Investment and Entrepreneurship*, 33(14):170-172.
- [17] Dworkin, S. L. (2012). Sample Size Policy for Qualitative Studies Using In-Depth Interviews. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 41(6): 1319-1320.